

THE IMPACT OF INFORMATION STRESS ON THE ADOLESCENT PERSONALITY

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Abstract: The rapid changes and developments observed worldwide are leading to the emergence of new tasks in the field of psychological practice. It is appropriate to shed light on the nature and causes of stress observed in humans. The modern stage of social development is the information age. As a consequence of globalization and at the same time as a factor ensuring it, we can recognize that the flow of information has expanded exponentially. Information is not limited to news from the world of sports, show business and art, but also provides information in political, scientific, artistic, official, unofficial, etc. fields, and the opportunity to easily obtain them has also appeared. Regardless of age, profession, interests, every person enters the world of information, receives, assimilates, and interacts with it. Adolescents can be considered a large segment of consumers of this wide range of information. It is no secret that a modern teenager lives in a complex world by the nature of his development.

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The rapid changes and developments observed worldwide are leading to the emergence of new tasks in the field of psychological practice. It is appropriate to shed light on the nature and causes of stress observed in humans. The modern stage of social development is the information age. As a consequence of globalization and at the same time as a factor ensuring it, we can recognize that the flow of information has expanded exponentially. Information is not limited to news from the world of sports, show business and art, but also provides information in political, scientific, artistic, official, unofficial, etc. fields, and the opportunity to easily obtain them has also appeared. Regardless of age, profession, interests, every person enters the world of information, receives, assimilates, and interacts with it. Adolescents can be considered a large segment of consumers of this wide range of information. It is no secret that a modern teenager lives in a complex world by the nature of his development.

The system of social structures that affect the dynamic development of the adolescent personality, including the family, school, informal associations, is undergoing dramatic changes under the influence of globalization. Also, information received through the media affects the emotional-volitional aspects and system of interests of adolescents, causing various disorders in their behavior and psyche. One of such disorders is stress, and it should be recognized that the essence of this concept is still controversial.

Stress is a state of strong and prolonged psychological tension in a person that occurs as a result of severe emotional tension of the nervous system. The positive effect of stress on a person that mobilizes is called eustress, and the negative effect is called distress. Eustress gives a person mental strength, encourages activity. Distress has a negative effect on a person. Its consequences can lead to mental, physical, emotional and spiritual stress, exhaustion of the body and increased blood pressure, heart failure, and stomach inflammation.

Stress is always subjective. The emergence and development of stress in adolescents depends on socialization in childhood. In particular, the mother's stubbornness, harshness, high demands,

disregard for someone else's opinion, or, conversely, the mother's passivity and lack of self-confidence can cause a child to become stressed. The father's lack of attention, aggressiveness and indifference - such forms of behavior make it difficult for the father and child to identify. The conflict of the family, the presence of a negative environment also affect socialization. As a result of late socialization in the family, the teenager becomes susceptible to stress, as he is going through the period of puberty.

There are several types of stress, but the most common type in recent times is informational stress. Informational stress is one of the types of emotional stress. The development of science and technology around us and its impact on humans is becoming stronger and more dominant than the impact of society and nature. The volume of information collected and created by humanity is expanding and is observed to expand further every decade, but the human brain and the number of cells that make it up have not changed, and the duration of education is increasing, which in itself poses a risk of increasing informational stress.

The brain has a wide range of capabilities to absorb information, and an increase in the volume of information is harmful, but if there is a need to process a large amount of information in a short time, this leads to severe nervous tension and causes informational stress, that is, the volume and speed of information entering the brain, which does not correspond to biological and social capabilities, also causes informational stress. Here, if the volume of information is one factor, and secondly, lack of time and personal motivation, social reasons are added to it, the brain's self-defense mechanism ceases to function, and a person cannot protect himself from informational stress. Adolescents appear as the most vulnerable group in this situation.

The negative consequences of informational stress in adolescents can be: a tendency to loneliness, distraction and forgetfulness, constant fatigue, apathy and weakness, sleep disorders, eating disorders, manifestation of causeless aggression, low self-esteem, lack of confidence in one's own strength.

In conclusion, it can be said that the negative situations arising as a result of the impact of globalization are a process that cannot be limited by artificial barriers. Therefore, it is advisable for each person to increase the possibilities of personal psychological safety to some extent. It is necessary not only to form self-defense capabilities, but also to exert the right educational influence on the adolescent child. In this regard, increasing the psychological literacy of the population is an urgent task. In addition, it is necessary to establish services related to the correct approach to the reception and sorting of information in the field of psychological practice.

References:

1. Stress and Coping Folkman, S., & Moskowitz, J. T. (2021). Stress, coping, and hope. New York, NY: Springer.
2. Digital Stress Appel, M., Marker, C., & Gnambs, T. (2020). Are social media ruining our lives? A review of meta-analytic evidence. *Review of General Psychology*, 24(1), 60–74.
3. Cyberpsychology Norman, K. L. (2021). *Cyberpsychology: An introduction to human-computer interaction* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
4. Mental Health and Social Media Fardouly, J., & Vartanian, L. R. (2022). Social media and body image concerns: Current research and future directions. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 45, 101289.

